

D8.5 REPORT ON APPLIED NLP SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

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Date: February 28, 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004984

Project Acronym: CLS INFRA

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Project Full Title: Computational Literary Studies Infrastructure

Grant Agreement No.: 101004984

Deliverable/Document Information

Deliverable No.: D8.5

Deliverable Title: Applied NLP Sentiment analysis

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Dissemination Level: PUBLIC

Document History

Version/Date

28/02/2025

Changes/Approval

Author/Approved by

The following report documents the work of Work Package 8 in the CLS Infrastructure Project. The general goals of this work package are to increase the ease of access and application to NLP tools, including for less-well-resourced languages, as well as their standardization.

The report is organized as follows: an explanation of aspect sentiment analysis as a method, and tools developed for this task. These tools are in the form of a notebook. These tools integrate work in both WP 6 and 7 which facilitates integration of the pipeline from data preparation, programmable corpora, to analysis and back.

Sentiment analysis (SA), a widely used text mining method for categorizing textual entities as positive, neutral, or negative, has faced criticism in literary studies for its limitations. Scholars argue that the rigid polarity scheme of contemporary SA tools is ill-suited to the nuanced and complex interpretive needs of humanist research. In response to the inherent limitations of traditional sentiment analysis (SA) tools in CLS, Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) has emerged as a promising alternative. Unlike conventional SA systems that assign a single polarity label at the document, paragraph, or sentence level, ABSA operates at a finer level of granularity by focusing on specific aspects within the text. ABSA systems combine multiple information extraction subtasks to identify and extract: 1) aspect terms, 2) aspect categories, 3) opinion terms, and 4) sentiment polarities.

Literature often transcends conventional linguistic structures, utilizing intricate and ambiguous expressions to convey the complexities of human emotions and experiences. Additionally, NLP tools inherently embed their own implicit sentiment theories and biases, introducing further opacity and potential distortions when applied to such material.

While presenting ABSA as a panacea would be an overstatement, exploring new methodologies to assess the applicability of NLP in Digital Humanities (DH) practice is essential. The work done for this report aims to respond to calls for an exploratory approach in NLP-infused literary analysis methodologies, guided by the principle that "a criticism of the tools and methods currently adopted in sentiment analysis is as necessary as a free exploration of its potential. (Rebora, 2023)".

The current divide raises the question of whether ABSA as a technique could be a way to circumvent the rigidity of conventional SA-models - granting a more fine-grained and explainable perspective on aspect representation and sentiment expression in literary text. Because of its capacity to generate more fine-grained annotations, ABSA may be used in CLS to formulate answers to literary-historical research questions which seek to understand the valence of a range of entities in large corpora. By means of a practical example, the discriminative system we introduce in this report, and which was described in Dejaeghere (2024), was used to analyze a dataset of comments on fanfiction about Greek mythology (Neugarten et al., 2024).

Answering to the calls for exploratory research and evaluation of NLP-based methods, the results of the work done in the framework of the CLSinfra project presents a pilot endeavor to create a set of tools to facilitate the use of ABSA-methodologies for literary-historical research contexts.

For ABSA, we created Jupyter notebooks containing the code for three workflows:

A lexicon- and rule-based approach was created for aspect extraction based on spaCy's noun extraction module, 2) opinion word identification using spaCy's POS-tagger to extract adjectives, adverbs and auxiliary constructions and 3) sentiment analysis based on the extracted opinion words using the multilingual SenticNet package BabelSenticNet. This package builds upon the SenticNet framework which utilizes a concept-level knowledge base, enriched with semantic and affective information, to facilitate multilingual sentiment analysis (Vilares et al., 2018). In the case of negated sentiment words, NLTK's synset module was used to fetch the word's antonym and generate a score.

A machine-learning based pipeline is developed in two steps. The aspect extraction task is tackled by training two Flair-based sequence taggers on the annotations. The notebook shows you how to change the embedding type (e.g.: BERT or MacBERTh, the latter was trained on English historical texts) (Devlin et al., 2018; Manjavacas et al., 2021). For the sentiment analysis task, the notebook shows you how to fine-tune BERT and MacBERTh models on a dataset of gold standard aspects. These embeddings subsequently serve as input for diverse machine learning classification architectures, including SVM, AdaBoost, Random Forest, and MLP classifiers.

A pipeline based on Generative AI was created using the LLM **Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1**. The model was prompted to 1) extract the aspects/entities in the dataset, and 2) perform ABSA using the entity and the sentence as input. The results are extracted in a structured JSON-format.

Best practices

Based on the experiments done Dejaeghere (2024), which technique the user decides to use depends on their end goals. **A rule-based system** will be more challenging to create given the limited availability of resources for niche languages, historical periods and/or literary domains. On the other hand, the creation of a rule-based system in CLS can still be justified in the case of small-scale applications with clearly delineated end goals, formulaic patterns present in the data which can easily be recognized by a rule-based system, and domain expertise.

A rule-based approach was created for aspect extraction through the following steps:

1. The off-the-shelf spaCy's noun extraction module is used to recognize aspects/entities in the dataset.
2. Opinion word identification was done using spaCy's POS-tagger. Opinion words are defined as adjectives, coordinating conjunctions and subordinating conjunctions.
3. Sentiment analysis based on the extracted opinion words and aspects is performed using the multilingual version of the [SenticNet](#) package (BabelSenticNet) in a 1-5 range. In the case of negated sentiment words, NLTK's synset module was used to fetch the word's antonym and generate a sentiment score based on this antonym.

A discriminative system, on the other hand, is more advisable in cases where 1) an adequate number of annotations are available for training a system and 2) the user wishes for the results of this model to remain close to the rationale of the annotation guide used to create the training data.

A generative system holds great promise for information extraction purposes, but one must tread with great care in using these systems. While powerful, these systems raise valid concerns regarding biases, hallucinations, reproducibility and opacity - making their evaluation for the Digital Humanities (DH) community all the more urgent.

Our notebooks cater to scholars who want to perform sentiment analysis, by showing them different modelling techniques. Specifically, we cater to aspect-based sentiment analysis. We assumed that ABSA would be a more useful approach in CLS, as it allows us to allot a sentiment value on, as the name says it, the level of the aspect/entity rather than on the level of the sentence, paragraph or document.

Each notebook is a more educational and step-wise version of the code which was used for research purposes (Dejaeghere et al., 2024). All notebooks show you how to start from a plain text corpus, transform it into a Pandas DataFrame and output an entity/aspect column which can then be exported as a .csv-file. We showcase different approaches to ABSA using an in-house annotated corpus of travel literature, which can easily be accessed via our GitHub page. The notebooks contain a line of code to load in a partition of this dataset which the user can play around with, run all the code in the notebooks and inspect the output of each action. The core idea is for these notebooks to serve as **an educational starting ground** which can be adapted to personal use-cases in CLS.

Jupyter Notebooks for sentiment analysis in CLS

Version

```
-----
inceptalytics  0.1.1
nervaluate     NA
nltk           3.9.1
numpy          1.26.4
pandas         2.2.2
sentinet       NA
sklearn        1.6.0
spacy          3.7.5
flair          0.15.0
torch          2.5.1+cu121
transformers   4.47.1
-----
IPython        7.34.0
jupyter_client 6.1.12
jupyter_core   5.7.2
notebook       6.5.5
-----
Python 3.11.11
```

Version Date

20/01/2025

Which Operating Systems does it work on?

- Windows
- Unix
- MacOS
- Linux

Licens e

- Fully free (do you need the exact name, e. g. CC-BY? Add it into parentheses!)

Distribution

- Cloud service

Where to download, how to install, documentation, user guides

- <https://github.com/GhentCDH/CLSinfra/tree/main> all information regarding the literary-historical annotations of the travel literature dataset, the Python packages, and the rationale behind the creation of the notebooks can be found on our GitHub which gets updated regularly.

User interface

- GUI
- API-REST

Docker instance

- Yes

How does the tool process your text?

- Automatically adds some labels (annotation) to your texts.

Does the tool allow you to export the results?

- Yes, the tool shows you how to apply information extraction and export the results as a .csv-file.

Is this tool a statistical model (or a set thereof)?

- No, however, the Notebooks use off-the-shelf statistical models, and shows you how to adapt them to your purpose.

Does this tool include statistical models? (Irrelevant, erase if this is a statistical model)

- Yes

Can you easily train and use your own statistical model with this tool ?

- Yes

XML-TEI compatibility

- The tool does not support XML-TEI at all.

How is an input document to be structured for the tool?

The notebook shows you how to apply sentiment analysis to an example dataset of annotated travel literature, which can be accessed and played around with in the Jupyter notebook environment. Given that this tool is a Jupyter Notebook showcasing possible NLP-pipelines for sentiment analysis, the way the input text is structured should eventually be adapted to your own data structure and goals.

Methods and features

We use a tool to solve a task. The tool is approaching this task with methods to provide some features or compute values of some metrics for the given text. Features typically enrich the input text (either in-line or stand-off) with labels or filter the text according to a query. Assigned labels typically belong to a given tagset (e. g. Universal Dependencies or Penn Treebank) or/and pertain to a formalism such as HPSG or minimalist syntax). Filters typically pertain to a query language (also a formalism).

Quick orientation for contributors	Task (what you want to achieve with that method)	Method (usually more generic than task)	Features/ Metric/ Formalism, Tagset
NLP	Sentiment analysis (aka Opinion mining, Emotion AI)		

Which human languages does the tool support (as of February 2023)?

Language	Variety (geographical, or temporal if not modern)
Any (it is language-agnostic)	
Dutch (not Flemish)	
English	
Flemish (not Dutch)	
French	
German	

Which other tools from this list does it integrate?

- Flair
- spaCy
- Transformers
- Torch

Papers

- Dejaeghere, T., Singh, P., Lefever, E., Birkholz, J., 2024. Exploring Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis Methodologies for Literary-Historical Research Purposes, in: Sprugnoli, R., Passarotti, M. (Eds.), Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Language Technologies for Historical and Ancient Languages (LT4HALA) @ LREC-COLING-2024. ELRA and ICCL, Torino, Italia, pp. 129–143.
- Devlin, J., Chang, M.-W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019). *BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding* (No. arXiv:1810.04805). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1810.04805>
- Manjavacas Arevalo, E., & Fonteyn, L. (2021). MacBERTh: Development and Evaluation of a Historically Pre-trained Language Model for English (1450-1950). In M. Hämmäläinen, K. Alnajjar, N. Partanen, & J. Rueter (Red.), *Proceedings of the Workshop on Natural Language Processing for Digital Humanities* (pp. 23-36). NLP Association of India (NLPAI). <https://aclanthology.org/2021.nlp4dh-1.4/>
- Neugarten, J., Dejaeghere, T., Singh, P., Hemmons, A. R., & Birkholz, J. M. (2024). *Catching Feelings: Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis for Fanfiction Comments about Greek Myth*. 217-231.
- Rebora, S. (2023). Sentiment Analysis in Literary Studies. A Critical Survey. *Digital Humanities Quarterly*, 017(2).
- Vilares, D., Peng, H., Satapathy, R., & Cambria, E. (2018). BabelSenticNet: A Commonsense Reasoning Framework for Multilingual Sentiment Analysis. *2018 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, 1292-1298. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SSCI.2018.8628718>

Jupyter Notebooks for sentiment analysis in CLS

Rule_based_ABSA

Version

```
-----  
inceptalytics    0.1.1  
nervaluate      NA  
nltk             3.9.1  
numpy           1.26.4  
pandas          2.2.2  
sentinet        NA  
sklearn         1.6.0  
spacy           3.7.5  
flair           0.15.0  
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IPython         7.34.0  
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- Yes

XML-TEI compatibility

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How is an input document to be structured for the tool?

Unknown or write some text here about formats and schemas.

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